

COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PREVALENCE OF CHOLELITHIASIS AMONG FEMALE AND MALE POPULATION OF GERONTOLOGICAL AGE IN THE FERGANA VALLEY DEPENDING ON AGE CATEGORIES

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Relevance. According to the WHO, in the modern treatment and diagnostic process of cholelithiasis (CSD) it is important, especially in individuals of the gerontological group (75-90 years and above), not only to provide scientific information on a certain type of treatment (surgical or conservative) and clinical and fundamental recommendations, but also to acquire modern innovative technologies acceptable for preventive surgery and the ability to use them. For the advanced development of CSD surgery in the 21st century, it is important to identify the most susceptible individuals with high or very high risk for this pathology and their special prevention to ensure the process of early detection, effective and safe treatment (with proper pharmacovigilance, pharmacoepidemiological screening) and the prevention of not only CSD itself, but also formidable complications of cholecystectomy, cholecystostomy, choledochotomy, choledochomyotomy and transduodenal sphincteropylotomy.

The aim of the study is to study the prevalence, pharmacoepidemiology of cholelithiasis and its main risk factors among the male and female unorganized population of the gerontological group of the Fergana Valley to enable scientifically based planning and optimization of early diagnosis, prevention and treatment of this disease.

The object of the study was a contingent of 4,500 individuals of the gerontological age population, formed using random number tables based on the nominal electoral lists of men and women in three regions of the Fergana Valley; as well as 779 patients with cholelithiasis who were undergoing inpatient treatment in the regional multidisciplinary hospitals of Andijan, Namangan and Fergana (for VEN analysis).

The subject of the study: were the results of general clinical and biochemical blood tests, survey, physical, instrumental and

pharmacoepidemiological monitoring; as well as the method of "daily nutrition reproduction" adapted to the peculiarities of Uzbek cuisine.

Research methods. To solve the set tasks, epidemiological, clinical, laboratory, biochemical, instrumental, pharmacoepidemiological and statistical research methods were used, as well as the "daily nutrition reproduction" method.

Results of the study. We analyzed the results of an epidemiological study on the prevalence of cholelithiasis among the female and male population of gerontological age in the Fergana Valley, depending on age categories.

The prevalence of cholelithiasis in the population of the gerontological group ≥ 60 - 90 years old, estimated by epidemiological criteria, was 42.5% among men and 57.5% among women ($\chi^2 = 0.222$; $P > 0.05$; $RR = 95\%$ $CI = 0.907 - 1.174$).

In the analysis, the closest associations of cholelithiasis with age were found. Relatively high rates of prevalence of cholelithiasis, both in men and women, were established in the group of men and women 60-74 and 75-89 years old; among the same groups ≥ 90 years old, reliably low rates of prevalence of cholelithiasis were noted. The prevalence of cholelithiasis in the age group of those examined was 35.3%, among the male population - 19.5% and among the female population - 15.8% ($\chi^2 = 4.091$; $P < 0.05$; $RR = 1.497$; 95% $CI = 1.010 - 1.504$). Among those examined aged 75 - 89 years, cholelithiasis was found with a prevalence rate of 45.2%, in men 19.0% and in women 26.2% [$\chi^2 = 0.007$; $P > 0.05$; $RR = 1.008$; 95% $CI = 0.830 - 1.224$]. Among those examined aged ≥ 90 years, the incidence of cholelithiasis was 2.69%, and among the male and female populations in this age category, it was established with a prevalence rate of 1.15% and 1.54%, respectively ($\chi^2 = 0.735$; $P > 0.05$; $RR = 1.404$; 95% $CI = 0.049 - 3.038$)

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